

Recognition of odonyms in Serbian language

Staša Vujičić*, Duško Vitas*, Miloš Utvić †

* Faculty of Mathematics
Studentski trg 16, 11 000 Belgrade, Serbia

† Faculty of Philology
Studentski trg 3, 11 000 Belgrade, Serbia
{stasa, vitas, misko}@matf.bg.ac.rs

Abstract

In this paper we present the problem of recognizing street names and other odonyms in ads in Serbian language in order to develop a system which automatically serves the users who make an offer or a demand. The experiment was limited to ads that are related to supply and demand of residential objects. The complexity of the model of representation of street names is, on one hand, due to them being multiply nested named entities, and on the other, to differently motivated variations in the structure of the same name. This paper presents the models of street names created through specially developed lexical resources and finite transducers in the Unitex system, as well as results of experiments of their application on the corpus of contemporary Serbian language and series of ads.

1. Introduction

Recognition of names of the streets, boulevards, avenues, roads, etc., is an integral part of the problem of recognition and categorization of named entities (Chinchor et al., 1999). In lexical analysis, they appear as multiword units or contingent sequences of more simple words. Their recognition as street names, apart from that as named entities, reduces the number of ambiguities in the text. For example, in the name of the street *Knez Mihailova ulica*, Knez Mihailo is not the owner of the street, but a significant figure in the Serbian history after whom the street got its name. The paper discusses the problem of recognition of street names in ad text and the corpus of contemporary Serbian language¹ in order to construct transducers that will annotate the recognized names with corresponding XML tags, in accordance with (Chinchor et al., 1999). In addition to recognizing the very street names, special transducers have been developed in the Unitex system that also recognize adjectives for a place that more closely describe the locations referred to in the ads. Identified names and complements of place are then used as input data for a query in a geographic information system in order to try to find the matching pairs of ads, if they exist, and thus meet the needs of users.

The class of street names is limited in the experimental phase, primarily to Serbian names. The corpus contains foreign names only in the exceptional cases. Odonyms of other languages are rarely found in the corpus of contemporary Serbian language, and the ones that are mostly well known odonyms such as *Manhetn* (*Manhattan*) or *Jelisejska polja* (*Elysian Fields*).

In the construction of transducers, lexical resources developed for Serbian language were used, especially dictionaries of proper names (Krstev et al., 2005a) and local grammars that have been developed by the bootstrap method proposed in (Gross, 1999), based on the analysis of the corpus of contemporary Serbian.

2. Description of the problem

The names of streets in the Serbian language are mostly constructed from the names of famous people, geographic concepts or important dates, so that identification of street names means identification of one or more nested named entities. Only exceptionally are those names neutral in relation to named entities (such as, for example *Slavujev venac* (*Nightingale's wreath*), *Cvetni trg* (*Flower square*) or *Cvetna ulica* (*Flower street*)).

The complexity of the problem of recognizing street names in the Serbian language stems from several sources rooted in the system of Serbian language.

According to the orthography of Serbian language, if the street name begins with the word *ulica* (*street*), the initial letter needs to be capitalized, thus *Ulica*; but if the word *ulica* is not in the first place, it is then written in lower case: *Ulica Simina* and *Simina ulica*. It is often deviated from this spelling rule in written texts, so the form *ulica Simina* can also be found in the corpus of modern Serbian language. Also, spelling of some personal names is subject to fluctuations. The proper name *Mihailo* is often written as *Mihajlo* (e.g. *Bulevar Miha (i + j) la Pupina*).

A street name can be written in Cyrillic or Latin alphabet, which in some cases leads to ambiguity in interpretation of the Latin name, as in the examples *Ulica Viljema Šekspira* (*William Shakespeare's street*) where *Viljem* has two Cyrillic representations (*Вилјем* and *Виљем*) or *Ulica Kralja Petra I Oslobodioca* where symbol *I* can be interpreted as a Roman numeral or conjunction *i* (*and*).

Serbian derivative system in many cases allows the replacement of the structure *ulica N* with *A+Pos ulica*, where *N* is a noun or noun phrase, and *A+Pos* the appropriate possessive or relational adjective. For example, *Ulica Kneza Mihaila* can be replaced by *Knez-Mihailova ulica*. Moreover, in such cases, it is often possible to omit the word *ulica*, so that only the adjective refers to the odonym (*Knez-Mihailova*), which introduces additional ambiguity. This possibility creates further complexity. If the street name is followed by a noun phrase, one of its parts is usually selected to move to the front of the name of the street. Thus, for example, *Ulica*

¹ <http://www.korpus.matf.bg.ac.rs>

Ilije Garašanina becomes *Garašaninova ulica* (possessive adjective of the last name), but *Ulica Vase Čarapića - Vasina ulica* (possessive adjective of the first name).

The street names that include toponyms consist a special problem. As a rule, the structure of these names is *A+Rel ulica*, where *A + Rel* is an appropriate relational adjective. For example, *Francuska ulica* (*French street*). In case the toponym is a multimember word, a complex transformation occurs within the string that refers to the toponym. For example, in the name of a street *Novosadska ulica* (*Novi Sad street*), *novosadska* is a relational adjective derived from a complex toponym *Novi Sad* (Utvić, 2008). In Serbian language, the possessive adjectives (for example, *novosadska*) are written with a small initial letter, except in this very case because of the orthography rule that the street names are written with an initial letter capitalized (*Novosadska ulica*). Considering the rich inflexion system of Serbian language, street names are subject to transformation rules of multimember words, where it is necessary to take into account the complex conditions of matching.

In addition to the problems listed, street names are subject to frequent change. Only 30 of over 5,000 streets in Belgrade have borne the same name for more than a century, while during the last four years more than 500 changed their name. Therefore, a custom model of description of the semantic relationships, based on the one developed within the project Prolex (Maurel et al., 2006), can be applied to identification of the street names indicating the same local toponym. Name change may apply to the change of the odonym type (e.g. *Ulica 29. Novembra* (*The street of the 29th of November*), became *Bulevar despota Stefana* (*Boulevard of Despot Stefan*)), but we should also keep in mind the cases of the exact same name occurring in two types of odonyms, indicating different locations (e.g. *Bulevar Nikole Tesle* (*Boulevard of Nikola Tesla*) and *Ulica Nikole Tesle* (*Nikola Tesla's*)).

3. Models

The first step in constructing a model for recognition of street names was creation of the dictionaries of possible street names.

Lexical resources developed for the Serbian language that are used for recognition are dictionaries of proper names (Krstev, Vitas and Gucul, 2005a), dictionaries of celebrities and a general dictionary of Serbian language. Below is an overview of the dictionary of proper names:

```
Vasa,Vasa,N1741+Hum+NProp+First+Nick+SR
Cyarapicx,Cyarapicx,N28+NProp+Hum+Last+SR
Cetkin,Cetkin,N1002+NProp+Hum+Cel+Hist
Bonaparta,Bonaparta,N1685+NProp+Hum+Cel+Hist
Klara,Klara,N1637+NProp+Hum+First+EN+Val=Clara+
```

The entries in the dictionary consist of a word form, lemma and part of speech and inflexion information. N stands for a noun, NProp stands for a proper name, Hum stands for human, First for the first name, Last for the surname, Nick for the nickname, Cel for celebrity and so on.

Here is an excerpt from the corpus of modern Serbian language with odonyms:

```
Preko Autokomande, pa u Ulicu Maksima Gorkog.
```

```
Potrcya niz ulicu. Nasta prava pometnxa.
```

```
Prodje zaobilazno, sporednim ulicama.
```

```
Iz jedne beogradske ulice, krajem osamdesetih
```

```
Preko Knez Mihailove ulice do Malog Kalemegdana.
```

```
Klub iz ulice Zdravka Cyelara.
```

```
Simbol Knez-Mihailove ulice svezdesetih godina.
```

The first thing to notice in the structure of street names in the corpus of contemporary Serbian language is that odonyms may appear after the words street (*ulica*), road (*put*), loop (*petlja*), alley (*sokače*), boulevard (*bulevar*), pier (*kej*), coast (*obala*), square (*trg*). In exceptional cases, when odonyms are of foreign origin odonyms words like avenue (*avenija*) or canal (*kanal*) can also be found.

The first structure that we can distinguish is the one with personal nouns. They appear, for example, in the following names: *Terazije, Slavija, Zeleni venac*.

The next structure that we see in the analysis of text and speech is in the form of the name of odonym, followed by the name of a famous person in genitive, or very similar forms of the name of odonym followed by names of several celebrities in genitive. So we have, for example, *ulica Lole Ribara, bulevar Milutina Milankovića, trg Nikole Pašića*. Particular attention should be paid to constructing a genitive form of names of male and female celebrities, which is discussed in detail in the paper (Krstev, Vitas and Gucul, 2005b). As synonymous to this structure, there is also a structure built from a possessive adjective resulting from the name of celebrities, optionally followed by the name of an odonym. For example, *Dositejeva, Simina, Dobračina*.

Another distinguished structure is the form of the name of odonym followed by the title and the name of the famous person in genitive, where more celebrity names can also appear. For example, *ulica Kneza Mihaila, ulica majke Jevrosime, ulica braće Jugovića, ulica poručnika Spasića i Mašare*.

There are two ways to present the structures of the form: name of an odonym, date, and name of an odonym, number and noun. Namely, it is allowed to write numbers which are part of the structure as words and signs for numbers, where one should also take into account whether the number is an ordinal, in which case it should be followed by a period. For example, *ulica 27. marta* (*The street of the 27th of March*) or *ulica Dvadeset i sedmog marta* (*The street of the twenty-seventh of March*), *ulica 1300 kaplara* (*The street of 1,300 corporals*).

The structures constructed from toponyms are built with relational adjectives. These structures are in the form: relational adjective, name of an odonym. Thus, for example, the street name *Makedonska ulica* is constructed from a toponym *Makedonija*, and similarly, *Mostarska petlja* is constructed from *Mostar* and *Balkanska ulica* from *Balkan*.

4. Presenting the models with finite automata

Odonym names used in the construction of other structures were placed in a separate subgraph *odonimi.grf*, given in the Figure 1.

Figure 1. odonimi.grf

In recognition of street names, a structure that can optionally follow the structures described in Chapter 3 can also be used, and it is separated into a special subgraph **broj.grf**. This graph recognizes the structures of type *u broju 3 (in number 3), na broju 3 (on number 3), u br 5 (in No 5), u br. 8 (in No. 8), broj 56 (number 56), br 9 (No 9), br. 80 (No. 80), 57*.

Also, when constructing the above described structures, we use subgraphs **datum.grf** and **imena.grf** that describe dates or names of famous people in genitive. Dates are constructed from ordinal numbers (the number followed by a period) and names of months, or ordinal numbers written in letters followed by the name of the month. In the graph **imena.grf** we use names of famous people, which are tagged with semantic categories *+NProp* (proper name) and *+Hum* (human) in the dictionary.

Therefore, the graph **ulicaPoznataLicnost.grf** is built from subgraphs **odonimi.grf** and **imena.grf**, and graph **ulicaTitulaPoznataLicnost.grf** from subgraph **odonimi.grf**, titles *<N+PropHum>* and subgraph **imena.grf** where conjunctions can also appear.

The graph **RelacioniPrivedUlica.grf** is built from the relational adjective of a toponym *<A+Rel+Nprop+Top>* followed by a subgraph **odonimi.grf**. and the graph **PrisvojniPrivedUlica.grf** is built from the possessive adjective of a famous person *<N+NProp:2>*, followed by a subgraph **odonimi.grf**.

The last step in this phase of the experiment is to expand the developed finite state automata that recognizes street names so it can tag the appearance of street names in the text with XML labels, in accordance with (Chinchor et al., 1999).

When such expanded graphs are applied to the corresponding resources, while prepositions deciding whether something is a street name or not are also included in the analysis, the result is the output with tagged street names, as shown in an excerpt below:

```
iz ulice Zdravka Cyelara<PREP+p2>iz</PREP+p2>
<ENAMEX>ulice Zdravka Cyelara</ENAMEX> prvo se
pilharica zvena iz Ulice 27.
marta<PREP+p2>iz</PREP+p2> <ENAMEX>Ulice 27.
marta</ENAMEX> broj 25 a.
```

```
i 27 marta 1941 na ulice Beograd <ENAMEX>ulice
Beograda</ENAMEX> i drugih gradova
Na uglu ulice Milena <ENAMEX>ulice
Milena</ENAMEX> se drzxala za ruku
na raskrsnici ove ulice i Ulice Slobodana
Penezicxa Krcuna <ENAMEX>Ulice Slobodana
Penezicxa Krcuna</ENAMEX>
kroz tunel koji vodi do Ulice Teodora
Drajzera<PREP+p2>do</PREP+p2> <ENAMEX>Ulice
Teodora
```

5. Application to the searching of ads

This paper is limited to ads in which housing is demanded or offered, regardless of whether it concerns apartments, houses, rooms, offices, garages, etc. and the possibility to answer three questions: "Who-whom?" , "what?" and "where?". In order for the latter stage of the experiment to offer full functionality, i.e. to synchronize the customer needs and offering: the very type of users "who-whom?" (male, female, family ...), in the form in which the ads are entered it is specified: whether the user offers or demands, the type of the object in question "what?" (room, apartment, house ...) and the address where the facility is located, including the details that further determine the user's wishes, in response to "where?": "blizu" (near), "u blizini" (close to), "u krugu" (within), "kod" (at), "preko puta" (opposite). This gives the following format of the ad:

```
<oglas id="1">
  <namenaa> ponuda/potražnja </namenaa>
  <objekat> soba/ stan/ kuća...
  </objekat >
  <tekst>...</tekst>
</oglas>
```

As it is presented at the beginning of this paper, the street name recognition, but also further clues on the location, are provided using the system Unitex. In addition to Unitex, which was used to identify street names in the text, GIS (Geographic Information System) will be used in the later stages of the experiment, in which maps of the city center with marked streets will be included. The references such as "u blizini" (close to), "oko" (around the), "u krugu" (within), ... allow the GIS system to call the appropriate functions and get the list of street names that match the required criteria, which can later be used in the re-searching of ads in order to find those ads that match the user's enquiry fully or with a certain threshold of tolerance.

By analyzing the ads with housing offers and demands, we concluded that users often do not provide completely accurate street names that would satisfy their needs, but rather use descriptions of locations in relation to the major objects in the certain area. Such objects are often described by colloquial names rather than formal, official names. For example, "kod bloka 70" (at block 70) or "kod Piramide" (near the Pyramid), define the same area of the city, which could be described more formally by the street name "u ulici Jurija Gagarina" (in the Jurija Gagarina's street).

The next step in the experiment would be to incorporate the detailed map of Belgrade into the GIS system, which, in addition to the marked streets, would contain information about facilities and points of interest, whether they are sights (libraries, monuments, fountains,

parks, forests ...), or shopping centers, markets and points that are referred to by their non-official names in everyday language, and to provide name recognition of such objects in texts of different types of ads.

6. Conclusion

In this paper we presented the basic structure of models for recognition of street names in the Serbian language and their practical application. It should be noted that, although currently achieved results are satisfying, work on this issue is at an early stage and has yet to be developed in future. In the later stages of the experiment, models for identifying street names should be enriched, more detailed maps of the city should be included and the possibilities of its search should be extended.

7. References

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